
HUMAN SUSTAINABILITY AND PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICAL FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE.

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Abstract: The study evaluated the human sustainability and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were; examine the relationship between continuous learning and revenue growth and evaluate the relationship between fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The area of the study was Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 267 selected civil servants was used. The whole population was used to due small number. Two hundred and fifty eight (254) respondents returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses tested using Z – test. The findings indicated that Continuous learning had significant positive relationship on the revenue growth, $Z = 10.416$. $P. = 0.05$ and Fairness had significant positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. $Z = 11.671$. $P. = 0.05$. The study concluded that Continuous learning and Fairness had significant positive relationship with the revenue growth and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State invest in regular training and development programs to ensure employees are up-to-date with industry trends, regulations, and new technologies.

Keywords: Human sustainability, continuous learning, fairness, revenue growth & operational efficiency.

1.1 Introduction

The pharmaceutical sector in any economy plays a prominent role in the general health of citizens residing in the country. Nigeria is not an exception. Owing to its significance in the general welfare of the economy, it is imperative to give serious attention to issues that concern this sector. The Nigerian pharmaceutical sector is known to be complex as it involves numerous players (manufacturers, national regulators, wholesalers and retailers, government ministries and other stakeholders). This means that there is need for these stakeholders to put in additional effort to create an enabling environment to exploit the full potentials of the sector (Efayena, Enoh and Buzugbe, 2018). The success of an organization is linked to the level/the ability of the organizations to sustain its human capital development. Organizations are defined based on the existence of positive ethnicity. Adopting sustainability strategy by organizations helps to boost organizations objectives as it helps to attract best talents who are more interested in the precedence of organizations ethics towards achieving high level of productivity and profit. Grant and Brock (2020) defined sustainability as the focus on meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs and also composed of economic, environmental, and social factors as its pillars (Murphy, 2019).

Performance is seen as a compartment of effectiveness and proficiency that covers operational and financial outcomes in the organization. As companies grow and the war for talent intensifies, it is increasingly important that training and development programs are not only competitive but are supporting the organization on its

defined strategic path. Performance measures assess the satisfaction the organizations stakeholders. Craig, (2018) opines that corporation sustainability typically looks at its impact on the community locally and globally, but sustainability starts with the people behind the scenes. It unites them to create a better work culture, work-life balance and contributions to customers and the world. Ensuring human sustainability doesn't detract from business goals, rather infusing the company with purpose can help attract motivated, skilled workforce that drives financial success (Chladek, 2019). It is on this background the study seeks to examine on the human sustainability and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu state.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Sustainability practices are recognized as the foundation for an entity's continuity and success in the green revolution era. Human sustainability determine future values for the competitive advantages, and increases the company's value in the areas of economic benefits, and financial profits employee motivation and retention. The pursuit of sustainability has prompted businesses to develop and implement deliberate measures and strategies to improve the environmental, economic, and social dimensions of corporate sustainability. Organizational performance is solely determined by how well it achieves its stated goals and objectives.

Sustainability is a long-term goal for society to meet the needs of economic growth at its current speed with the least amount of impact on the environment. Human sustainability practice foster a work environment that prioritizes employee well-being, development, and long-term value creation, ensuring that individuals that thrive both professionally and personally, contributing to the organization's sustained performance over time; it encompasses aspects like work-life balance, career growth opportunities, mental health support, diversity and inclusion, and a strong sense of purpose, ultimately aiming to attract and retain top talent while minimizing burnout and attrition. Organizations that take a human sustainability stand are more likely to see better company results, including better engagement and diversity metrics, or significantly lower employee turnover numbers.

Human sustainability is the idea businesses need to follow through and act upon in order to make sure they are prioritizing and taking good care of such interactions. The challenges would be ameliorated through promoting work-life balance, prioritizing employee well-being through mental health initiatives, fostering a positive workplace culture, implementing flexible work arrangements, providing adequate training and development opportunities, encouraging open communication, setting realistic performance expectations, and addressing burnout through proactive measures; and all aimed at ensuring employees can perform sustainably over time without compromising their health and personal lives. However, neglect to this importance would be of negative impact to the organization which will lead poor quality of service and deteriorating profit in the organization.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to evaluate the human sustainability and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The specific objectives were;

- i. Examine the relationship between continuous learning and revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research question guided the study;

- i. What is the relationship between continuous learning and revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the relationship between fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State?

1.5 Statement of the Hypotheses

- i. Continuous learning has positive relationship on the revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.
- ii. Fairness has positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study will be significant to the following;

Organization: The study is important to organizations because it can lead to better employee retention, productivity, and company culture. It can also help organizations improve their social and environmental impact. It also help to treats employees well, leading to higher retention, better productivity, and a positive company culture.

Employees: The study is very important to employee because it motivates employees as they feel more considered and respected by the organization. It encourage employees to use natural resources responsibly. It means conserving energy, water, and other resources while still producing the necessary products or services. By creating a healthy environment, companies can reduce their impact on the planet and protect valuable resources.

Customers: The study is important to customers because it can lead to a better brand reputation, increased loyalty, and a competitive advantage. The importance of sustainability to consumers is becoming increasingly apparent, as they feel increasingly engaged, threatened, yet helpless.

Researchers: The study is important to researchers because it can help them create new ideas and solutions to global challenges.

2.0 Review of the Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Human

Humans are omnivorous, capable of consuming a wide variety of plant and animal material, and have used fire and other forms of heat to prepare and cook food since the time of Homo erectus. Humans have had a dramatic effect on the environment. A human is a bipedal hominin characterized by having a higher and vertical forehead compared with earlier hominins (Roopnarine, 2018).

2.1.2 Sustainability

Sustainability is crucial for the health of our planet and the well-being of present and future generations. Practicing sustainability involves the responsible and balanced use of the planet's resources. Sustainability allows individuals and businesses to address pressing environmental challenges such as climate change, pollution, and resource depletion. Sustainability in business refers to integrating environmental, social, and

economic considerations into organizational practices and everyday operations (PwC, 2023). Sustainability is a concept related to the development of products, goods, and services that involves meeting our present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to fulfill their own needs. Sustainability as a concept recognizes that the environment is an exhaustible resource. Sustainability is the ability to maintain a specific rate or level. In a business context, it's about maintaining or improving profitability without doing harm (Biela-Weyenberg, 2023).

2.1.3 Human sustainability

Human sustainability in the organization helps to maintaining the organization human capital. Human capital is a private good of individuals, rather than between individuals or societies. The health, education, skills, knowledge, leadership and access to services constitute human capital. Human resource department is regarded as the agent of sustainability in any given organization (Murphy, 2019) Human sustainability in the manufacturing firm helps firms to manufacture high quality products at a low price for survival and sustainability. Human development without being sustainable cannot be true human development. Human development is what sustainability proponents want to sustain and without sustainability, human development is not true human development (Neumaver, 2020). Human sustainability is understood as an investment in human capital, recognising that people are a critical component of the planet's sustainability equation. Human sustainability can be distilled into a multifaceted concept centered on the holistic wellbeing of individuals within the framework of sustainable development (Jarnhamn, 2024).

2.1.4 Components of human sustainability

Amelia (2024) state four components of human sustainability as follows: social sustainability, economic sustainability, and environmental sustainability. The components used in the study explained below;

2.1.4.1 Continuous learning

Continuous learning is the practice of consistently increasing one's knowledge. It can be done for personal or professional reasons. It is the ongoing expansion of knowledge and skill sets. In the context of professional development in the workplace, it's about developing new skills and knowledge, while also reinforcing what has been previously learned (Hashemi-Pour and Chai, 2022).. Continuous learning means that people are learning new skills or gaining knowledge continuously (Timon, 2023). Continuous learning is the process of learning new skills and knowledge on an on-going basis. This can come in many forms, from formal course taking casual social learning. It involves self-initiative and taking on challenges. Continuous learning can also be within an organization, or it can be personal, such as in lifelong learning. Staying competitive in today's global marketplace means that organizations need to be innovative, adaptive, and ever-changing. Achieving this depends on the skill and knowledge of the workforce (Ivan, 2022). Continuous learning, also referred to as lifelong learning, is the practice of expanding your skills and knowledge as part of an ongoing process of self-improvement or professional development (Rumage, 2024).

2.1.4.2 Fairness

Fairness is an ethical principle that speaks to how we treat one another in our social and economic interactions. Managers that seek to improve the fairness of relationships between the firm and employees, as well as within the supply chain, may see positive effects on organizational performance (Yeoman and Santos. 2019). Fairness

is the idea of treating people equally and with respect, and making decisions without bias. It's a moral judgment that involves considering all relevant factors to reach a reasonable outcome. Fairness is important because it promotes trust, respect, and equality. It can also help to create a sense of justice and community wellbeing. Fairness is a top driver for employees to give extra effort in their job, a key element for innovation and productivity. Fairness and equity in the workplace forms a key part of limiting conflict and ensuring that employees are provided with an environment that encourages productivity and opportunities. Fairness suggests to people that their membership in the organisation is valued and that the organisation respects them, thereby making commitment to the organisation a viable way of maintaining one's identity and fulfilling one's interests. Fairness in the organisation is very important, as the management of the relationship between workers and employees must be just and honest (Ekong, and Abiodun, 2020).

2.1.5 Performance

Performance of employees is a regular assessment and evaluation of employees' job performance. Workwise, (2019) defines performance as a management approach to help businesses achieve its goals through the planning of critical performance targets and the measurement of progress towards those targets. Evaluating employees' performance helps employers to set clear expectations in the organization and also measure employees' success. Performance in the manufacturing firm is related to effectiveness and efficiency (Ugwu; Ebeke and Igah, 2021). Organizations are in a constant search for performance; they want to achieve performance or to improve performance, or more often, to measure the achieved performance level. Overall employee performance will lead to business growth and expansion In the study Eze, Olorunda, &Mbah, (2021), performance is the process of calculating the financial results of an organization's activities and policies (Eze et al., 2021). It is used to assess a company's overall financial standing over a certain time period and may also be used to compare similar companies within the same industry or to aggregate industries or sectors (Balaman, 2019). Performance management is a process in which the employer monitors, evaluates, examines and communicates with employees to make sure that their performance is aligning with the companies' expectations and goals (Mishra, 2024).

2.1.6 Components of performance

Jack (2024) outline the three components of performance include: planning, cultivation, and accountability. The components used in the study explained below.

2.1.6.1 Revenue growth.

Revenue growth refers to an increase in revenue over a period of time. In accounting, revenue growth is the rate of increase in total revenues divided by total revenues from the same period in the previous year. Revenue growth can be measured as a percent increase from a starting point. Revenue growth is the increase in a company's total revenue or income over a specific period, typically calculated quarterly or annually (Emilia, 2024). Revenue growth is a company's income over a specific time period compared to an identical time period in the past. For example, the money your company made this year versus last year. Revenue growth is how much a company's revenue increases on a month-to-month basis. When calculating revenue growth, you solve for the percentage of growth. This is a common metric startup companies use to measure how rapidly they're growing. Revenue growth is the increase (or decrease) in a company's sales from one period to the

next. Revenue growth is a key measure of a company's success. Revenue growth is a key performance indicator expressed as a percentage, representing how able company is to grow its revenue over a period. Revenue refers to the money a business earns from all sources, including sales, investments, interest, royalties, and more, before any expenses are deducted (Nathan, 2024).

2.1.6.2 Operational efficiency

Efficiency no doubt impacts on the performance of firms. One of the most important goals of company management is to maximize its effectiveness current and future financial and business performance as they affect market price per share and shareholder wealth. Efficient firms perform better than inefficient firms in every sense. Operational efficiency is primarily a metric that measures the efficiency of profit earned as a function of operating costs. The greater the operational efficiency, the more profitable a firm or investment is. This is because the entity is able to generate greater income or returns for the same or lower cost than an alternative (Adam, Andy and Suzanne, 2024). Operational efficiency helps product and service-based businesses drive process improvement for reduced costs and increased profit margin. The benefits of optimized efficiency include reduced operational expenses and increased profits, a more satisfied workforce, and increased sustainability and flexibility (Lucija, 2024). Optimizing operational efficiency can be a shortcut to improved performance and higher profits. It is a vital ingredient in the recipe for business success. Businesses that streamline their operations to maximize productivity and minimize waste often find themselves ahead of the curve. By optimizing every aspect of operations, businesses can significantly reduce costs. For instance, a manufacturing company that implements lean manufacturing principles to eliminate waste and improve process flow will reduce its production costs, which directly impacts its bottom line (Ebule, 2024).

2.1.7 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework draws upon existing theories, models, or established bodies of knowledge to provide a structure for understanding the research problem. It defines the scope of research, identifying relevant variables, establishing research questions, and guiding the selection of appropriate methodologies and data analysis techniques. (Singh, 2023).

2.2 Theoretical framework

The following theories guided the study, Human relations theory by Elton Mayo 1932; and goal-setting theory by Dr. Edwin A. Locke, 1968. The study was anchored on goal-setting theory because it states that goals are strongly associated with human performance. Goal-setting provides both a 'target' to work towards as well as a standard by which to evaluate performance.

2.2.1 The human relations theory of management

Human relations theory was developed by Elton Mayo 1932. Human Relations management theory is a premise of organizational psychology from the early twentieth century, which suggests that employee productivity and motivation can be increased through positive social bonds in the workplace and acknowledgement of the worker as a unique individual. It holds that improved working conditions (empowerment, participation, positive treatment) lead to increased productivity (Ward, 2021). Human relations management theory is a management approach that recognizes employees as human beings with needs and wants beyond their job tasks (Miranda and Shari, 2024). The Human Relations theory has human beings at its center as can be understood by the name, but it also had more to it. It viewed human beings not as machine models but as individuals with differing psychological motivations and with distinct and dynamic group behavior affecting performances (Ugwu, Ebeke and Igah, 2021).

This theory in support of objective one of the study, human relations falls under the umbrella of human resources. The human relations management theory is belief that people desire to be part of a supportive team that facilitates development and growth. Therefore, if employees receive special attention and are encouraged to participate, they perceive their work as having significance and are motivated to be more productive, resulting in high-quality work. (Miranda and Shari, 2024).

2.2 Goal setting theory

Dr. Edwin A. Locke developed the goal-setting theory of motivation in 1968. The theory suggested that goals and objectives which an employee establishes enhance their motivation for their performance. This is because employees go an extra mile to see that their goals are achieved and objectives are met. If these objectives are not achieved, they will either modify to make them more achievable or improve their performance. In case they choose to improve their performance, it will result in achievement of performance measurement practices aims (Salaman, 2005). Performance is improved by specific and ambitious goals in comparison to easy or general goals. If an employee accepts a set goal, has the capability to attain it and is not disoriented by conflicting goals, the expected outcome is a positive linear relationship between goals and performance (Locke 1968).

In support with objective two of the study ‘continuous learning’ because it explains that creating specific, measurable, and difficult goals unlocks higher performance in individuals compared to easy goals that merely ask them to try their best. The presence of these goal characteristics results in increased motivation in employees, which ultimately leads to higher levels of workplace success. The theory also shows the relationship between goals and self-efficacy, which is an individual’s confidence in achieving a given task. The theory provide direction and a standard against which progress can be monitored, challenging goals can be achieved. An effective goal creates excitement and energy in employees. It is consistent with the values, objectives, and strategic advantages of the organization. Effective goal setting facilitates unified action consistent with the vision of organization (Chetty, 2019).

The study was anchored on goal-setting theory because it encourage continuous learning in employees by establishing specific, achievable goals. These goals can help employees feel motivated and accomplished which can lead to a cycle of growth and learning. Goal-setting theory is a concept that describes the strong link

between goal setting and task motivation. Goal-setting theory refers to the effects of setting goals on subsequent performance. The goal-setting theory states that specific and challenging goals with appropriate feedback contribute to improved performance.

2.2 Empirical review

2.3.1 The relationship between continuous learning and revenue growth

Ezeh and Mbah (2016) conducted a study on the effectiveness of human resources training and development strategy as a motivation in manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The objectives were to examine the effectiveness of employee health and safety as motivation in manufacturing firms in Enugu state and find out the extent of effectiveness of promotion and welfare measures as motivation in manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The study used the survey approach. A population of 384 staff was used for the study. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis, and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient and Fstatistic (ANOVA) tool. The findings showed that there is effectiveness of employee health and safety as a motivation in selected manufacturing firms in Enugu state is significantly high and there is effectiveness of promotion and welfare measure as a motivation in manufacturing firms in Enugu state is significantly high.

Orga, Ekechukwu and Mbah (2018) conducted a study on the performance appraisal as bedrock for the growth of Nigerian Money Deposit Banks in South East, Nigeria. The objectives was to: ascertain the effect of performance appraisal on the income of Nigerian money deposit banks; evaluate the effect of performance appraisal, on product sales of Nigerian money deposit banks, determine the effect of performance appraisal on banks' value of Nigeria money deposit banks. The study used the survey approach. The study population was a total number of 4,503. The sample size for the study was 346. The study employed Pearson correlation coefficient (r) for data analysis. The finding showed that performance appraisal has a significant positive effect on income; and there is significant positive effect of performance appraisal on bank value on Nigeria money deposit banks.

Eetu (2020) conducted a study on the employees' continuous learning and job satisfaction - effects on productivity. Lappeenranta University of technology school of industrial engineering and management. Master's thesis. The objective was to examine the effect of continuous learning and job satisfaction. The study adopted a qualitative case method. The findings showed that more face to face interaction is needed between employees for learning because much of the knowledge of the process is tacit and so difficult to share in other ways.

Ozoko & Ede (2020) conducted a study on the effect of learning on the product quality of chemical and pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The objectives were to examine the effect of employee absorbed knowledge on the standard product of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, ascertain the effect of employee undergoing a process on the features of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria and determine the effect of employee retention of knowledge on the reliability of the product of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study used the survey approach. A population of 3,418, and sample size of 346 was used. The findings indicated that employee absorbed knowledge has positive effect on standard product of manufacturing firms in Enugu State

Ugwu, Ebeke and Igah (2021) conducted a study on the effect of human sustainability on the performance of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study sought to evaluate the effect of investment in health on the quality of services of the selected food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu state and examine the effect of investment in education on the profitability of the selected food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study used the survey approach. A population of 4250 and 352 staff of sample size was used. The data were analyzed using Regression method. The findings showed that Investment in health had positive effect on the quality of service, and investment in Education had effect on the profitability of selected food, beverage and tobacco manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

Besim and Samir (2024) conducted a study on the impact of lifelong learning and investments in employee development on employee productivity and performance. The study sought to investigate the profound impact of lifelong learning initiatives on employee performance within various professional settings. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The findings showed that the pivotal role of lifelong learning in fostering a culture of adaptability, skill enrichment, and heightened problem-solving capabilities among employees. The study concluded that a commitment to lifelong learning not only contributes to improved individual performance but also impacts organizational outcomes.

2.3.2 The relationship between fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

Efayena, Enoch and Buzugbe (2018) examined on assessing efficiency in the pharmaceutical sector of Nigeria. The study sought to examine the firms' efficiency under the constant returns to scale (CRS) and variable returns to scale (VRS) assumptions. The study uses a non-parametric technique (Data Envelopment Analysis) to analyze the data. The finding shows inefficiency in the pharmaceutical sector as it operates under a decreasing return to scale. The study concluded that, for an appropriate policy mix to stimulate the efficiency of the pharmaceutical sector in Nigeria by enhancing research and development as well as regulations within the sector

Amna, Ali and Syed (2018) conducted an empirical relationship between operational efficiency and profitability (Evidence from Pakistan Exploration Sector). The study sought to examine the relationship between total asset turnover, fixed assets turnover, debtor's turnover, current ratio and quick ratio. The study employed Ordinary least square, correlation matrix and descriptive. The findings showed that the total assets turnover, debtor's turnover and quick ratio have strong negative impacts on the profitability measured by ROE, of firms. The current ratio and fixed asset turnover have positive impacts on the return on equity. The study concluded that efficiency as measured by (total assets turnover, debtors' turnover, and quick ratio that to have a better picture more data is needed.

Hassana and Cross (2020) conducted a study on the effect of supplier development on operational performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The objectives are to; determine whether supplier technical support has statistically significant effect on competitive advantage; early supplier involvement has statistically significant effect on cost efficiency; and also Ascertain whether supplier audit has statistically significant effect of supplier financial supports on operational efficiency at Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Product and Service Solution (SPSS). The

population was fifteen thousand and twenty six; and the sample size of three hundred and ninety was used. The finding showed that supplier technical support has statistically significant effect on competitive advantage, early supplier involvement has statistically significant effect on cost efficiency, supplier audit has statistically significant effect on operational efficiency, and supplier certification has statistically significant effect on customer service delivery at Dangote Sugar Refinery Plc

Olubunmi and Folajimi (2020) conducted a study on the effect of environmental fairness on assets utilization in the Nigerian oil and gas companies: An empirical analysis. The study sought to evaluate on environmental fairness and its effects on assets utilization. The population was twelve. Inferential statistics was adopted. The finding showed that environmental fairness had a statistically and positively significant impact on asset utilization

Sathish & Gaonkar (2023) carried out a study on the evaluation of operational efficiency of fair price shops in public distribution system: an empirical study. The study sought to evaluate the operational efficiency of Fair Price Shops in the State of Goal. The study adopted survey research design. The population of five hundred was used. The finding showed that an efficient public distribution system in the form of efficient fair price shops will ultimately benefit the ration card holders at large ensuring food and nutritional security.

2.4 Summary of the review

Based on the review, human sustainability on the performance it is the degree to which an organization values its employees as human beings. It involves creating a workplace that improves the health, well-being, and skills of its employees. Sustainable human resource management is a way to achieve human sustainability by integrating sustainability into human resource practices. It represents a more integrated way into the consciousness of corporate organizational responsibility, learning and development of making profit and being efficient on the marketplace, which is designed to support long-term sustainable organizational goals and outcomes by balancing people, the state of wellbeing. To improve sustainability performance, organization can adopt a holistic approach by setting clear goals aligned with the values and conducting regular audits.

The theories guided the study as follows; human relation theory, and goal-setting theory. The empirical review were carried out according to objectives of the study (independent and dependent variable). In the previous studies like; Eetu (2020) examined on the employees' continuous learning and job satisfaction - effects on productivity; Besim and Samir (2024) conducted a study on the impact of lifelong learning and investments in employee development on employee productivity and performance. Amna, Ali and Syed (2018) conducted an empirical relationship between operational efficiency and profitability (Evidence from Pakistan Exploration Sector); Olubunmi and Folajimi (2020) conducted a study on the effect of environmental fairness on assets utilization in the Nigerian oil and gas companies: An empirical analysis. Most of the previous studies were conducted in Nigeria and few were carried out outside Nigeria. However, the study was motivated to bond the gap in knowledge.

2.5 Gap in knowledge

The few studies done were carried outside the human sustainability and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State and did not focus to best of my knowledge on the continuous learning and revenue growth; fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. Most of the studies reviewed analyzed their

data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression while the present study made use of Z test to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling this research gap by evaluating the human sustainability and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

3.0 Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu State, Nigeria. The state has many pharmaceutical manufacturing firms, out of this firms five were selected for the study. The selected firms were Cinnamon Drugs Limited, Plot C9 Emene Industrial layout, Emene Enugu State; Gloria-G Pharm Ltd, Behind NRC Junior staff Quarters, Asata, ENUGU; Impact Pharmaceutical Limited., Plot 33A/34A, Standard Industrial Layout Extension, Opposite ANAMCO, Emene, Juhel Nigeria Limited, 35 Nkwubor Road, Emene, Nemel Pharma Industries Ltd, 4 A/B Medical Road, Phase 6, Trans Ekulu, ENUGU. These organizations were selected due to the number of staff and high ethical standard. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 268 selected owners and employees of the study organizations was used. The whole population was used to due small number. Two hundred and fifty four (254) respondents returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 85 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.92 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using Z – test statistic tool.

4.2 Data Presentation

4.2.1 The relationship between continuous learning and revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State

Table 4.2.1.1: Responses on the relationship between continuous learning and revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Pharmaceutical companies rely on continuous learning to stay at the forefront of scientific advancements	605 121 47.6	224 56 22.0	54 18 7.1	70 35 13.8	24 24 9.4	977 254 100.0	3.85	1.390	Agree
2	Ongoing training and knowledge acquisition enable researchers and developers to innovate, creating new drugs or improving existing ones.	655 131 51.6	272 68 26.8	57 19 7.5	8 4 1.6	16 16 12.6	1008 254 100.0	4.03	1.339	Agree
3	Continuous learning leads to the introduction of cutting-edge products to the market, which boost revenue through higher sales	830 166 65.4	192 48 18.9	54 18 7.1	20 10 3.9	12 12 4.7	1108 254 100.0	4.36	1.087	Agree

4	Continuous learning helps employees stay updated on regulatory requirements and compliance protocols, preventing costly fines or delays in product launches	715 143 56.3	272 68 26.8	39 13 5.1	10 5 2.0	24 24 9.8	1060 254 100.0	4.18	1.246	Agree
5	Firms that prioritize continuous learning often create a culture of growth and development, which helps attract and retain top talent	470 94 37.0	364 91 35.8	39 13 5.1	50 25 9.8	31 31 12.2	954 254 100.0	3.76	1.364	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.036	1.2852	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.1.1, 177 respondents out of 254 representing 69.6 percent agreed that Pharmaceutical companies rely on continuous learning to stay at the forefront of scientific advancements with the mean score of 3.85 and standard deviation of 1.390. 199 respondents representing 78.4 percent agreed that Ongoing training and knowledge acquisition enable researchers and developers to innovate, creating new drugs or improving existing ones with a mean score of 4.03 and standard deviation of 1.339. 214 respondents representing 84.3 Percent agreed that Continuous learning leads to the introduction of cutting-edge products to the market, which boost revenue through higher sales mean score of 4.36 and standard deviation of 1.087. 211 respondents representing 83.1 percent agreed that Continuous learning helps employees stay updated on regulatory requirements and compliance protocols, preventing costly fines or delays in product launches with mean score of 4.18 and standard deviation of 1.246. 185 respondents representing 72.8 percent agreed that Firms that prioritize continuous learning often create a culture of growth and development, which helps attract and retain top talent, with a mean score of 3.76 and standard deviation 1.364.

4.2.2 The relationship between fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

Table 4.2.2.1: Responses on the relationship between fairness and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 DA	1 SD	∑FX	- X	SD	Decision
1	When employees feel treated fairly, they are likely to be more motivated and productive, which lead to improved operational efficiency	555 111 43.7	64 16 6.3	249 83 32.7	18 16 6.3	28 28 11.0	914 254 100.0	3.65	1.377	Agree
2	A commitment to fairness enhance a pharmaceutical firm’s reputation, fostering trust with consumers, regulatory bodies	900 180 70.9	64 16 6.3	87 29 11.4	18 9 3.5	20 20 7.9	1089 254 100.0	4.29	1.264	Agree
3	Fairness in a firm's culture encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing among employees	705 141 55.5	64 16 6.3	195 65 25.6	8 4 1.6	28 28 11.0	1000 254 100.0	3.94	1.367	Agree

4	When teams feel empowered and treated equitably, they are more likely to innovate, and develop new drugs and improving production processes.	790 158 62.2	208 52 20.5	69 23 9.1	22 11 4.3	10 10 3.9	1099 254 100.0	4.33	1.067	Agree
5	Properly managing costs while being fair to consumers can improve the firm's efficiency without sacrificing ethical standards.	930 186 73.2	104 26 10.2	57 19 7.5	22 11 4.3	12 12 4.7	1125 254 100.0	4.43	1.107	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.128	1.2364	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.2.2.1, 127 respondents out of 254 representing 50.0 percent agreed that When employees feel treated fairly, they are likely to be more motivated and productive, which lead to improved operational efficiency with the mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.377. 196 respondents representing 77.2 percent agreed that a commitment to fairness enhance a pharmaceutical firm’s reputation, fostering trust with consumers, regulatory bodies with a mean score of 4.29 and standard deviation of 1.264. 157 respondents representing 61.8 Percent agreed that Fairness in a firm's culture encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing among employees with mean score of 3.94 and standard deviation of 1.367. 210 respondents representing 82.7 percent agreed that when teams feel empowered and treated equitably, they are more likely to innovate, and develop new drugs and improving production processes with mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation of 1.067. 212 respondents representing 83.4 percent agreed that properly managing costs while being fair to consumers can improve the firm's efficiency without sacrificing ethical standards, with a mean score of 4.43 and standard deviation 1.107.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

4.3.1 Continuous learning has positive relationship on the revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Pharmaceutical companies rely on continuous learning to stay at the forefront of scientific advancements	Ongoing training and knowledge acquisition enable researchers and developers to innovate, creating new drugs or improving existing ones.	Continuous learning leads to the introduction of cutting-edge products to the market, which boost revenue through higher sales	Continuous learning helps employees stay updated on regulatory requirements and compliance protocols, preventing costly fines or delays in product launches	Firms that prioritize continuous learning often create a culture of growth and development, which helps attract and retain top talent
N	254	254	254	254	254
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum 1 Maximum 5	1 5	1 5	1 5	1 5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive .476 Negative -.476	.533 -.533	.654 -.654	.581 -.581	.478 -.478
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	7.592	8.502	10.416	9.255	7.624
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $7.592 < 10.416$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that Continuous learning had significant positive relationship on the revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.592 < 10.416$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Continuous learning had significant positive relationship on the revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

4.3.2 Fairness has positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	When employees feel treated fairly, they are likely to be more motivated and productive, which lead to improved operational efficiency	A commitment to fairness enhance a pharmaceutical firm’s reputation, fostering trust with consumers, regulatory bodies	Fairness in a firm’s culture encourages collaboration and knowledge sharing among employees	When teams feel empowered and treated equitably, they are more likely to innovate, and develop new drugs and improving production processes.	Properly managing costs while being fair to consumers can improve the firm’s efficiency without sacrificing ethical standards.	
N	254	254	254	254	254	
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum Maximum	1 5	1 5	1 5	1 5	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute Positive	.437	.709	.555	.622	.732
	Negative	.110	.079	.110	.039	.047
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		-.437	-.709	-.555	-.622	-.732
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	6.965	11.294	8.847	9.914	11.671
		.000	.000	.000	.000	

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $6.965 < 11.671$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that Fairness had significant positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.965 < 11.671$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 (2-tailed test at 95 percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Fairness had significant positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Continuous learning had significant positive relationship on the revenue growth

From the result of the hypotheses one, the calculated Z- value ranges from $7.592 < 10.416$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 which implies that Continuous learning had significant positive relationship on the revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review, Ezech and Mbah (2016) conducted a study on the effectiveness of human resources training and development strategy as a motivation in manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study used the survey approach. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis, and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient and Fstatistic (ANOVA) tool. The findings showed that there is effectiveness of employee health and safety as a motivation in selected manufacturing firms in Enugu state is significantly high and there is effectiveness of promotion and welfare measure as a motivation in manufacturing firms in Enugu state is significantly high. Orga, Ekechukwu and Mbah (2018) conducted a study on the performance appraisal as bedrock for the growth of Nigerian Money Deposit Banks in South East, Nigeria. The study used the survey approach. The study employed Pearson correlation coefficient (r) for data analysis. The finding showed that performance appraisal has a significant positive effect on income; and there is significant positive effect of performance appraisal on bank value on Nigeria money deposit banks.

4.4.2 Fairness had significant positive relationship on the operational efficiency

From the result of the hypotheses two, the calculated Z- value ranges from $6.965 < 11.671$ against the critical Z- value of 0.000 which implies that Fairness had significant positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review, Efoyena, Enoch and Buzugbe (2018) examined on assessing efficiency in the pharmaceutical sector of Nigeria. The study uses a non-parametric technique (Data Envelopment Analysis) to analyze the data. The finding shows inefficiency in the pharmaceutical sector as it operates under a decreasing return to scale. Amna, Ali and Syed (2018) conducted an empirical relationship between operational efficiency and profitability (Evidence from Pakistan Exploration Sector). The study employed Ordinary least square, correlation matrix and descriptive. The findings showed that the total assets turnover, debtor's turnover and quick ratio have strong negative impacts on the profitability measured by ROE, of firms. The current ratio and fixed asset turnover have positive impacts on the return on equity. The study concluded that efficiency as measured by (total assets turnover, debtors' turnover, and quick ratio that to have a better picture more data is needed.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. Continuous learning had significant positive relationship on the revenue growth of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. $Z = 10.416$. $P. = 0.05$.

- ii. Fairness had significant positive relationship on the operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. $Z = 11.671$. $P. = 0.05$.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that Continuous learning and Fairness had significant positive relationship with the revenue growth and operational efficiency of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. Human sustainability plays a crucial role in the performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State. The integration of sustainable human resource practices, such as employee well-being, skill development, and effective leadership, enhances productivity and drives organizational growth. By fostering a conducive work environment, promoting work-life balance, and prioritizing employee health and development, pharmaceutical firms can boost both operational efficiency and long-term success. Human sustainability, therefore, remains a pivotal factor for ensuring competitive advantage and sustained performance in the industry.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. It is recommended that pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State invest in regular training and development programs to ensure employees are up-to-date with industry trends, regulations, and new technologies. This will enhance their skills, improve productivity, and foster innovation within the firm.
- ii. It is essential that firms implement transparent and equitable policies for promotions, compensation, and performance evaluations. Ensuring that all employees are treated fairly will promote a positive work culture, increase job satisfaction, and ultimately contribute to higher employee retention and improved organizational performance.

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